

EFFECT OF RE -ENTRANT CORNER SEVERITY ON SEISMIC PERFORMANCE OF PLAN IRREGULAR RC BUILDINGS USING RESPONSE SPECTRUM AND PUSH OVER ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Irregular building configurations are increasingly adopted in modern construction due to architectural and functional requirements. However, plan irregularities such as plus-shaped and single cut-out structures significantly influence seismic behavior by inducing torsional effects, stiffness discontinuity, and stress concentration at re-entrant corners. The present study investigates the seismic performance of plan-irregular reinforced concrete (RC) buildings through linear and nonlinear analysis procedures. Three-dimensional models of multi-storey RC buildings, including a regular building, a plus-shaped building, and a single cut-out building, are developed using ETABS. Linear dynamic analysis is carried out using Response Spectrum Analysis in accordance with IS 1893 provisions, while nonlinear static analysis (Pushover Analysis) is performed based on ATC 40 guidelines to evaluate the inelastic seismic behavior and structural performance levels. The seismic response of the models is assessed by comparing parameters such as storey displacement, storey drift, load carrying capacity, roof displacement at performance point. Capacity spectrum curves are obtained in both X and Y directions to determine the performance point and evaluate the overall structural behavior under earthquake loading. The result indicate that the plan irregularity significantly affects the seismic performance of RC buildings. The plus-shaped building exhibits higher lateral displacement, increased storey drift, and pronounced torsional behavior due to severe re-entrant corner effects and reduced lateral stiffness. In contrast, the single cut-out model demonstrates comparatively better seismic performance.

Keywords : Plan irregularity, re entrant corners , plus shaped building, single cut out buildings, response spectrum analysis, pushover analysis seismic performance, RC building.

INTRODUCTION

Rapid urbanization and architectural demands have lead to the increasing adoption of irregular building configurations in modern construction. Among these plan irregularities such as plus shaped ang single cut out geometries are commonly used to satisfy functional and aesthetic requirements. However such configuration introduce discontinuities in the structural system resulting in complex seismic behaviour when subjected to earthquake loading. One of the main critical features associated with plan irregular building is the presence of re entrant corners which tends to concentrate stress and induce torsional effect.

During seismic events building with re entrant corners and diaphragm discontinuity exhibits non uniform distribution of mass and stiffness leading to different lateral displacement and increased vulnerability to damage. The severity of these plays a crucial role in determining the overall seismic performance of structure. Despite several studies addressing plan irregularities, limited attention has been given to the quantitative assessment of irregular configuration such as plus shaped and single cut buildings.

Conventional linear analysis methods are often insufficient to predict the actual seismic performance of irregular buildings under strong ground motion. Therefore, advanced seismic evaluation techniques such as Response Spectrum Analysis and Nonlinear Static Analysis (Pushover Analysis) are essential for understanding the inelastic behaviour and structural performance of these buildings. Response Spectrum Analysis provides an efficient estimation of peak dynamic response, whereas pushover analysis evaluates the progressive formation of plastic hinges and structural capacity under increasing lateral loads.

In the present study, the seismic performance of plan-irregular RC buildings is evaluated using ETABS software. Three-dimensional models consisting of a regular building, a plus-shaped building, and a single cut-out building are developed and analyzed. The analyses are carried out in accordance with IS 1893 provisions and ATC 40 guidelines. Key response parameters such as storey displacement, storey drift, base shear, roof displacement, and performance point are compared to assess the influence of plan irregularity on structural behaviour.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Several researchers have investigated the seismic behaviour of reinforced concrete (RC) buildings with plan irregularities, particularly those having re-entrant corners and diaphragm discontinuities. These irregular configurations are highly susceptible to torsional effects, stress concentration, and uneven stiffness distribution during earthquake excitation.

Md. Nazmul Hassan et al. examined the seismic behaviour of multi-storey RC buildings with re-entrant corners using Equivalent Static Analysis and Response Spectrum Analysis. The study reported that irregular buildings experience higher storey displacement, drift, and torsional response compared to regular configurations.

Jahanvi Suthar and Sharad kumar Purohit investigated the seismic behaviour of various re-entrant dominant RC frame buildings including C-, L-, T-, and plus-shaped structures. Their research concluded that increasing plan irregularity significantly affects lateral stiffness and seismic vulnerability.

A case study conducted by **C. Shreyasvi et al.** evaluated buildings with re-entrant corners under seismic loading. The authors observed that plan irregular structures showed increased displacement and drift compared to regular buildings and recommended nonlinear analysis methods for accurate seismic assessment.

Kevin Karanja Kuria and Orsolya Kegyes-Brassai reviewed the importance of pushover analysis in performance-based seismic engineering. The study emphasized that nonlinear static analysis helps identify plastic hinge formation, performance point, and collapse mechanisms more effectively than conventional linear methods.

Kshithij G. Raj and Roopanjali S. reviewed the seismic behaviour of irregular structures using pushover analysis and concluded that buildings with plan irregularities are more vulnerable to earthquake-induced damage due to uneven distribution of stiffness and mass.

Based on the literature, it is observed that most previous studies focused on conventional irregular configurations such as L-shaped and T-shaped buildings. Limited research has comparatively evaluated plus-shaped and edge cut-out RC buildings using both Response

Spectrum Analysis and Pushover Analysis. Therefore, the present study aims to assess the seismic performance of such plan-irregular structures and evaluate the influence of re-entrant corner severity on structural behaviour under earthquake loading.

OBJECTIVE

- To evaluate the seismic performance of plan-irregular RC buildings.
- To compare the behavior of plus-shaped and single cut-out buildings.
- To perform Response Spectrum Analysis using ETABS.
- To conduct Pushover Analysis and obtain capacity spectrum curves.
- To compare storey drift, displacement, and load carrying capacity.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology adopted in this study involves modelling, analysis, and comparative evaluation of plan-irregular reinforced concrete buildings subjected to seismic loading. The entire analytical procedure is carried out using ETABS structural analysis software.

Initially, three-dimensional models of multi-storey RC buildings are developed. The study includes one regular building model and two plan-irregular models, namely a plus-shaped building and a single cut-out building. The structural dimensions, material properties, loading conditions, and support conditions are assigned in accordance with relevant Indian Standard codes.

1.Response Spectrum Analysis (RSA)

A linear dynamic analysis is conducted to determine the peak structural response under earthquake excitation. The response spectrum is defined according to IS 1893 provisions considering seismic zone factor, importance factor, response reduction factor, soil type, and damping ratio.

2.Pushover Analysis

Nonlinear static analysis is performed based on ATC 40 guidelines. Incremental lateral loads are applied to the building model until the target displacement is achieved. Plastic hinges are

assigned at critical beam and column locations to simulate inelastic behavior and progressive structural failure.

Plan dimension	30 m × 30 m
Bays	6 x 6
Spacing	5m
Storeys	G +10
Storey height	3m
Column	450 x 450 mm
Beam	230 x 600 mm
Slab	150mm thick

Table 1 : plan and dimensions

Zone factor (Z)	0.36
Importance factor (I)	1
Response reduction factor (R)	5
Soil type	Medium

Table 2 : seismic factors

MODELLING

At first 3D model of a multi storeyed building is developed using ETABS. From the model diaphragm of the building is also developed. Total 3 models are prepared with plan irregularities . One building model (S1), with plan irregularity which has single cut-out at the edge of the building and another model (S2) with plan irregularity which is a Plus shape Building and a regular building.

fig 1: plan and 3D view of single cut out building

Fig 2: plan and 3d view of plus shaped building

Fig 3: plan and 3D view of regular building

CAPACITY SPECTRUM CURVE

The capacity spectrum curve obtained from nonlinear static analysis in X and Y direction of model S1 is shown in figure 4 and figure 5. The ultimate lateral load carrying capacity of building at performance point is around 8102.60 KN and the corresponding roof displacement is 46 mm in X-direction and ultimate lateral load carrying capacity of building at performance point is around 8108.15 KN and the corresponding roof displacement is 46 mm in Y-direction

Fig.4 : Capacity Spectrum Curve in X-direction (S1)

Fig.5 : Capacity Spectrum Curve in Y-direction (S1)

Fig 6: deformed shape

The capacity spectrum curve obtained from nonlinear static analysis in X and Y direction is shown in figure-7 and figure 8 for model S2. The ultimate lateral load carrying capacity of building at performance point is around 5311.94 KN and the corresponding roof displacement is 45 mm in X-direction and ultimate lateral load carrying capacity of building at performance point is around 5312.41 KN and the corresponding roof displacement is 45 mm in Y-direction.

Fig :7 Capacity Spectrum Curve in X-direction (S2)

Fig8. : Capacity Spectrum Curve in Y-direction (S2)

Fig.9 : Deform Shape of S2 Model

RESULTS

Response Spectrum Analysis

Storey	Regular	Edge Cut-Out	Plus Shape
11 (Roof)	48	58	75
10	45	55	70
9	41	50	60
8	37	45	54
7	32	39	47
6	27	33	40
5	22	27	33
4	18	22	27
3	14	17	20
2	10	12	14
1	6	7	8
Base	0	0	0

Table 3: Storey Displacement Table (mm)

Fig 10: Storey Displacement (mm)

Storey	Regular	Edge Cut-Out	Plus Shape
11	3	3	5
10	4	5	10
9	4	5	6
8	5	6	7
7	5	6	7
6	5	6	7
5	4	5	6
4	4	5	7
3	4	5	6
2	4	5	6
1	6	7	8
Base	0	0	0

Table 4 : Storey Drift Table (mm)

Fig 11: Storey Drift (mm)

Pushover Analysis

The comparison of load carrying capacity of building and displacement at the performance point are shown in figures- and figure respectively. The results obtained from this study show that building with re-entrant corner is inherently vulnerable to collapse due to earthquake load.

Fig 12: Comparison of Load Carrying Capacity of Different Model

Fig 13 : Comparison of Displacement at Performance Point of Different Models

CONCLUSION

➤ Effect on Displacement

- The regular building exhibits the least displacement, indicating higher stiffness and uniform load distribution.
- The edge cut-out model shows a moderate increase (~20–25%) in displacement due to reduction in slab continuity and edge stiffness.
- The plus-shaped building shows the maximum displacement (up to ~75 mm at roof), mainly due to:
 - Plan irregularity
 - Cantilever-like wing behavior
 - Reduced lateral stiffness
 - This confirms that irregular geometry significantly increases lateral flexibility.

➤ Effect on Storey Shear

- The base shear remains nearly constant for all models, as it depends on total seismic mass.
- However, force distribution varies slightly:
 - Regular building → uniform distribution
 - Cut-out → slight redistribution
 - Plus shape → concentration near junctions
 - Indicates that geometry affects force path, not total seismic demand.

➤ Effect on Storey Drift

- The regular building shows minimum drift and stable inter-storey behavior.
- The edge cut-out structure shows increased drift due to localized stiffness reduction.
- The plus-shaped structure exhibits maximum drift, especially at:
 - Upper storeys
 - Wing extremities

This highlights that plan irregularity increases drift and deformation demand.

➤ Torsional Behaviour

- Regular building → negligible torsion

- Edge cut-out → moderate torsion
- Plus-shaped building → significant torsional effects

Due to:

- Uneven stiffness distribution
- Re-entrant corners
- Asymmetric load paths

➤ Seismic Performance

- Regular structure → best seismic performance
- Edge cut-out → acceptable with proper detailing
- Plus-shaped building → critical case requiring special design attention

➤ Design Implications

➤ Irregular buildings require:

- Dynamic analysis (Response Spectrum / Pushover)
- Enhanced ductile detailing
- Strengthening at critical zones (edges, junctions)
- Drift control becomes a governing part in design

- RC frame building with diaphragm discontinuity has more lateral load carrying capacity as compared to the building with re-entrant corner.
- Model S1 has 34.5% more load carrying capacity than model S2.
- At performance point, the building having re-entrant corner may collapse during earthquake because of greater displacement in Y-direction as it has 66.66 % of re-entrant corner.
- The building with plan asymmetry needs higher column section to obtain the performance point.
- The buildings having irregular plan configuration has experienced more damage during the earthquake as compared to the building having simplified plan configuration

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